

ENHANCING WOODWORKING LESSONS: AN INQUIRY INTO PLANNING OF PRACTICAL LESSONS FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING IN UMGUNGUNDLOVU DISTRICT, KWAZULU NATAL, SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

Woodworking or "Crafts" class, often overlooked in today's digital age, plays a pivotal role in nurturing a well-rounded education that extends beyond the confines of textbooks and classrooms. Therefore, engaging in woodworking in schools is significant because it fosters intellectual growth by challenging learners' critical and creative thinking skills. It is fundamental to know that woodworking teachers need to have adequate lesson planning skills to ensure that workshops are well organized and lesson objectives are met without a hitch. Thus, in Technology and Vocational Education (TVE), lesson planning remains a crucial step to be practiced in order to accumulate effective teaching in a workshop. This study aims to enquire into planning of woodworking practical lessons for effective teaching in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal, South Africa. Purposive sampling was used to identify a total of eight woodworking teachers to participate in this study. Qualitative research method was used where document analysis and semi-structured interviews were used as a complementary data collection tools. A thematic analysis was used to analyze the collected data in this research. The findings reveal that woodworking teachers rely on the Civil Technology Practical Assessment Task (PAT) document that provides them with a template for PAT management plan for their practical lessons. Also, this study found that woodworking teachers oversight the need of preparing a lesson plan. However, this study recommended that KwaZulu Natal Department of Education should also emphasize on instructional planning skills when providing teacher development programs in order to promote effective teaching in schools.

Keywords: Woodworking, Effective teaching, Lesson planning, Civil Technology, Technology Education

INTRODUCTION

In this modern education system, craftsmanship programs have long been a point of focus in the curriculum within Technology and Vocational Education (TVE) system (Huma et al., 2022). Thus, TVE equips individuals with the practical skills and knowledge required for careers involving applied science and modern technology (Edokpolor & Owenvbiugie, 2017). Furthermore, it bridges the gap between skilled crafts and professional professions by preparing graduates for occupations crucial in various industries. Therefore, the main objective of TVE is to prepare graduates for the real world or careers classified above skilled crafts but below engineering professions. Yet, the curricula for TVE are specialized across a broad range of fields to cater to specific engineering industry needs. Thus, subject like Civil Technology in the secondary school level play a vital role to ensure that learners graduate with invaluable hands-on experience (Mtshali & Msimango, 2023). Hence, the main aim of Civil Technology is to ensure that learners are in a position to “demonstrate understanding of the industry, enhance knowledge, skills, values and reasoning abilities as well as establishing connections to life outside the classroom and address real-world challenges” (DBE/PAT, 2018:29). According to (Msimango, 2024), Civil Technology refers to a field of study and practice that focuses on three subject specialisations like civil services, construction and woodworking. Where, Civil services can be construed as plumbing, which focuses on installing a sewage system to enable the removal of storm water and wastewater from a site, as well as providing cold and hot water supplies to a building. Yet, the creation of bricks and concrete structures within the built environment is the main emphasis of construction. Woodworking plays a crucial role in a building environment. Hence, it concentrates on timber-framed buildings, including roof trusses, windows, doors, and other architectural details. Furthermore, it has contributed immensely to the aesthetic value of most commercial and domestic buildings to date (Mabasa et al., 2023).

Globally, woodworking is one of the most common subject specialisations practiced from the secondary school level. According to Cennamo et al. (2024), hands-on learning is a critical component of woodworking education in Austria. Hence learners are encouraged to engage directly with materials and tools in workshop settings where they can apply their theoretical knowledge practically. This experiential learning helps reinforce concepts and allows students to develop their skills through practice (Budhai, 2021). However, Austrian woodworking programs incorporate modern technology into the curriculum, such as Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machinery and advanced design software to ensure effective teaching and learning (Calquin et al., 2024). By familiarizing learners with these technologies, teachers prepare them for contemporary woodworking practices and enhance their employability in the industry. Additionally, this focus on modern methodologies not only enhances effective teaching of woodworking craftsmanship but also aligns educational outcomes with industry needs. Also, woodworking education in Austria encourages creativity among learners by allowing them to design their own projects from concept to completion. However, this process involves woodworking teachers' instructional planning and critical thinking—skills that are essential for success after every woodworking lessons. Therefore, woodworking teachers guide students through this creative process by providing mentorship rather than direct instruction, fostering an environment where students feel empowered to explore their ideas while still receiving constructive feedback (Clapp et al., 2016).

Currently, woodworking education in Nigeria, particularly within technology and vocational institutions, involves a structured approach that combines theoretical knowledge with practical skills (Isa & Kamin, 2019). Woodworking teachers begin by providing foundational knowledge about woodworking tools, safety practices, and material properties. This instruction is designed to take place in a classroom setting where learners learn about different types of wood, their characteristics, and appropriate uses. Furthermore, lesson plans are utilized by teachers as a guideline for practical skill demonstrations in order to effectively impart knowledge. Following theoretical instruction, learners engage in practical workshops where they apply what they have learned. These workshops are equipped with various tools and machinery necessary for woodworking tasks (Broun, 2018). Thus, this hands-on experience is crucial for developing proficiency in using tools safely and effectively. South African institutions provide a wide range of courses that cover essential woodworking techniques such as measuring, cutting, shaping, joinery, and finishing. Technology education curriculum is designed for both beginners and advanced learners, ensuring that individuals at different skill levels can find suitable training options (Martinez, 2022). Hence, woodworking is a dominant Civil Technology's subject specialization that was reintroduced in South African secondary and technical schools back in the year 2016 through Curriculum Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS). Therefore, in many South African schools woodworking hands-on learning experience is emphasized. Thus, this emphasis of woodworking practical approach may not only help students develop their hand-on skills but also prepares them for real-world applications in the woodworking industry (Igaru, 2023). The availability of workshops equipped with modern tools further enhances the learning experience.

Although this Civil Technology's subject specialization is still dominant in schools but the number of learners who enroll for this subject depreciates yearly. Hence, the study by Mabasa, Mtshali, Makgato and Skosana (2023) titled "Do we have a master plan to prevent the extinction of Civil Technology woodwork specialization in South African schools" also gives a concern about the smaller number of learners' enrolment for this particular subject. The findings from these scholars' study were too limited and clearly focusing only to the long-term plans while the dilemma is still on motion. Furthermore, their findings include the refurbishment of woodworking workshops, allocation of enough time for woodwork practical sessions and increasing operational budget for woodwork activities; and they believed that may rescue the looming extinction of this subject. However, this study is arguing with the use of depending only on the long-term plans to eradicate this problem. Moreover, this insight an existing gap of poor lesson planning that may lead to such unfortunate state for this valuable subject (Olabiyi, 2024). Currently, Woodworking teachers in schools encounter a variety of challenges that can hinder their ability to effectively teach students (Olabiyi, 2024). Recent studies have revealed that many South African schools are still facing budget constraints that limit the availability of tools, equipment, and materials necessary for effective woodworking teaching and learning. Inadequate resources can hinder students' ability to engage in projects and develop essential skills (Adeniran, 2020). Additionally, outdated or poorly maintained equipment can pose safety risks and affect the quality of education provided. Also, instructional planning skills is emerging as the challenge that hinder teachers to effectively teach learners of different needs in a workshop. Hence, students come with varying levels of experience, skill sets, and learning styles, which can complicate teaching efforts (Costa et al., 2020). Woodworking teachers must adapt their teaching methods to accommodate these differences, ensuring that learners receive personalized attention and support tailored to their individual needs. Thus, such threats pose a concern about Civil Technology teachers' instructional planning methods to ensure effective teaching of practical lessons in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal of South Africa.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to inquiry into planning of practical lessons for effective teaching in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal, South Africa. Engaging lesson plans is essential for effective teaching and fostering active participation in the classroom (Haryani et al., 2021). Also, poorly planned lessons that lack creativity or interactive elements can lead to disengagement among learners, resulting in decreased motivation and attentiveness (Fredricks, 2014). Thus, it is fundamental to know that woodworking teachers need to have adequate lesson planning skills to ensure that workshops are well organized and lesson objectives are met without a hitch. Adequate planning for practical lessons may promote the best use of woodworking instructional time as teachers can easily deliver coherent lessons, leading to efficiencies in teaching and learning. Furthermore, learners' interest in woodworking can be well captured hence learners may spend valuable class time trying to decipher unclear instructions and exploring their creativity skills.

RESEARCH PURPOSE

The purpose of this study is to enquire into planning of practical lessons for effective teaching in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal, South Africa.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How do woodworking teachers plan their practical lessons?
2. What are the challenges faced by teachers in planning practical woodworking lessons?
3. What are the teaching strategies used by woodworking teachers in the uMgungundlovu District?

LITERATURE REVIEW

INSTRUCTIONAL PLANNING

Instructional planning is essential to effective teaching, it is imperative that all teachers of technology and vocational subjects acquire this expertise. According to Stepniak (2019) "A teacher's plan which uses learning standards, the school curriculum, helpful tactics, helpful material, and information for meeting the requirements of all students" is what is meant to be understood when one refers to instructional planning. Therefore, accepting that teachers are fully prepared to meet every learner's educational objective is the aim of lesson planning (McConnell et al., 2020). In Sweden, as in many educational systems worldwide, lesson planning or instructional planning is a fundamental aspect of teaching practice that supports effective classroom instruction and student learning outcomes. Policymakers and teacher educators worldwide are focusing more on how teacher candidates get practical teaching experience and how to firmly establish teacher education in the process of classroom instruction (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Donaldson, 2011; Furlong et al., 2014; Moon, 2016; Munthe & Conway, 2017). According to (Jónsson et al., 2021), woodworking teachers in Sweden are responsible for planning and implementing their lessons based on the curriculum set by the Swedish National Agency for Education (Skolverket).

Furthermore, the curriculum provides the goals, objectives and general principles that teachers need to follow. Technology Education subject teachers are supposed to develop lesson plans that are in line with curricular objectives and make sure that students are fulfilling the necessary goals at various phases of their education, even if there is no explicit law regarding the techniques of instruction that can be employed (Msimango & Mtshali, 2024). In Sweden, woodworking practical lessons, known as "träslöjd," are typically integrated into the curriculum of elementary schools. These lessons aim to introduce students to woodworking skills and craftsmanship from an early age. Moreover, In Sweden, woodworking classes are part of the standard school curriculum (Fahrman et al., 2015). However, using such lessons, students not only develop their woodworking skills but also learn about design, craftsmanship, and the properties of wood as a material (Mirante, 2021). They gain an understanding of construction techniques, form expression, and artistic concepts related to working with wood. Overall, the preparation for woodworking practical lessons in Sweden focuses on providing students with a hands-on learning experience that fosters creativity, skill development, and an appreciation for craftsmanship from an early age (Sjöqvist et al., 2021). However, with well-crafted lesson plans, teachers not only hone their skills in instructional design but also acquire the expertise of carpentry and woodworking.

Explaining the significance of the Woodworking and Carpentry subject in Swaziland's pre-vocational education curriculum is crucial at this point (Hlophe, 2019). This programme was introduced into the school system in Swaziland in response to a number of issues and challenges that had been identified as being the most important aspect for future school's outcome. After Swaziland gained its independence in 1968, woodworking was added to the list of optional subjects offered in high schools. This course was offered as part of the Technical Studies curriculum, which also included technical drawing, metalworking, and woodworking (Hlophe, 2019). These days, this subject is a part of the Design and Technology set of disciplines, which also covers studies of metals and plastics that are referred to as "resistant materials." The way vocational topics are taught and learned in schools is generally influenced by a number of factors. Misconceptions regarding prevocational education, a lack of facilities and teaching resources, a shortage of teachers with the necessary qualifications, a lack of finance, and a lack of industry attachment are some of these reasons (Gwembire & Katsaruware, 2013; Kiadese, 2011; Ramdass et al., 2005). Thus, due to the shortage of teachers with adequate and necessary qualification skill this means the effective teaching and learning will be jeopardised because of teachers without appropriate instructional skills.

In South African schools, teachers prepare woodworking lessons by following a structured approach that combines theoretical knowledge with practical skills (Maeko, 2020). Therefore, Civil Technology' woodworking teachers are expected to ensure that the lesson plan for practical skills is in line with the prescribed learning outcomes and objectives for woodworking education (Mokhothu, 2022). Furthermore, teachers need to design a detailed lesson plan, outlining the specific topics, activities, and resources they will use during each session. Thus, lesson plans often include a mix of theoretical instruction, hands-on demonstrations, and student practice time (Hong et al., 2020). Previous studies have revealed that most teachers in the KwaZulu Natal province, South Africa do not practice instructional planning properly. In a study by Khuzwayo and Mashiya (2015) the synthesis of findings revealed a lack of uniformity and incompetent teachers in lesson planning and the scholars further recommended that issue to be the main critical issues that need attention of teachers' trainers, education department's officials and publishers. This means teachers are using a generic planning method which is not appropriate for effective teaching of woodworking practical skills. However, prior to conducting woodworking

practical lessons; woodworking teachers from uMgungundlovu, KwaZulu Natal, South Africa are expected to gather and prepare the necessary resources for the woodworking lessons. This may include tools, materials, safety equipment, instructional materials such as a cutting list, diagrams or videos, and any other items needed to facilitate effective teaching and learning in the workshop (Msimango, 2024). Also, their lesson plans must not only include curriculum objective only but learners must be also taught about safety and security in their work place. Civil Technology teachers must always ensure that they include effective teaching strategies on their woodworking subject specialisation lesson plans. Since, effective teaching strategies are essential for fostering a positive learning environment in the classroom (Zajda, 2018). Thus, teaching strategies in woodworking have numerous benefits; hence they encourage learners to become actively engaged with the material and help them develop critical thinking skills (ODUGBEMI & AIGBODUWA, 2023). Moreover, they foster creativity and innovation among learners by encouraging independent thought. However, it's important to note that these benefits can only be achieved if the teaching strategies are implemented correctly and effectively. Therefore, the KwaZulu Natal Department of Education (KZNDOE) must ensure that teachers receive adequate training to make it easy for them to prepare and conduct woodworking practical lessons effectively.

CHALLENGES FACED BY TEACHERS IN PLANNING PRACTICAL WOODWORKING LESSONS

According to Kimonen and Nevalainen (1996), in Finland, teachers face several challenges when planning practical woodworking lessons. One of the primary challenges faced by teachers in Finland when planning practical woodworking lessons is the limited availability of resources (Pöllänen & Urdziņa-Deruma, 2017). This includes a lack of tools, equipment, and materials necessary to conduct hands-on woodworking activities. Thus, without adequate resources, woodworking teachers may struggle to provide learners with meaningful practical experiences (Mabasa et al., 2023). Also, lack of skills in managing resources effectively plays a crucial role in depriving effective lesson planning for woodworking practical lessons. Hence, woodworking classes require access to a range of tools, materials, and workspace (Lee, 2023). Teachers must plan lessons that make efficient use of these resources while ensuring that each student has the opportunity to practice essential skills. Furthermore, these challenges can impact the effectiveness of the lessons and the overall learning experience for learners. Planning practical woodworking lessons can present various challenges for teachers, especially when aiming to provide engaging and effective instruction to students (Molande et al., 2017).

In Namibia, teachers face several challenges when planning practical woodworking lessons (Josua et al., 2022). These challenges can hinder the effective planning and delivery of the curriculum and impact learners' learning experiences (Soubra et al., 2022). The lack of materials is one of the main issues Namibian teachers confront while organizing hands-on carpentry classes (Brunette, 2006). Certain tools, supplies, and equipment are needed for woodworking and may not always be available in schools. Moreover, insufficient resources can limit the range of projects that can be worked on and the amount of hands-on learning opportunities available to learners (Leal Filho et al., 2016). Another significant challenge is infrastructure constraints. Many technical schools in Namibia may not have dedicated woodworking workshops or spaces equipped for practical lessons. This lack of appropriate infrastructure can make it difficult for teachers to conduct hands-on activities safely and effectively (Mtshali & Msimango, 2023). Inadequate workshop facilities can also impact the quality of instruction and limit the scope of projects that

can be undertaken. Furthermore, effective teaching of practical woodworking requires specialized skills and knowledge. However, teachers in Namibia may face challenges related to limited training opportunities and professional development in woodworking techniques (Josua, 2022). Yet, without adequate training, woodworking teachers may struggle to design engaging lessons, demonstrate proper techniques, and provide individualized support to learners during practical activities.

Teaching practical woodworking lessons in South African schools presents unique challenges for teachers. These challenges stem from various factors, including limited resources, lack of specialized training, and outdated curriculum. Similar to most African nations, South Africa faces a shortage of resources for the effective teaching of practical woodworking lessons. Thus, the lack of materials is one of the main issues South African teachers face when preparing hands-on woodworking lessons. Specific tools, supplies, and equipment are needed for woodworking and may not always be available in schools. Insufficient resources can limit the range of projects that can be worked on and the amount of hands-on learning opportunities available to learners. Furthermore, planning practical woodworking lessons within the constraints of limited class time can be challenging (Solomon et al., 2024). Therefore, teachers need to structure their lessons effectively to cover necessary content, provide hands-on practice, and allow time for individualized instruction and feedback.

The matter of technology and vocational subject teachers who lack skills of integration of theory and practice have never been left unnoticed in South African schools; which is also resulted from poor instructional planning for practical lessons. Yet, woodworking lessons should ideally integrate theoretical knowledge with practical skills (Nkwanyane, 2023). Furthermore, balancing the theoretical aspects of woodworking, such as design principles and wood properties, with hands-on practice poses a challenge for teachers in planning comprehensive lessons (Okillan Asianut, 2021). Lastly, in this current modern education system adapting to incorporating technology still pose a challenge to South African teachers hence digital technologies have invaded the education sector. Although, the uMgungundlovu District, in KwaZulu Natal is one of the best locations which contains a number of advanced higher education institutions that focus on technology education. However, advancements in technology impacting various industries, including woodworking, teachers may face the challenge of incorporating modern tools and techniques into traditional woodworking lessons (Ogbuanya et al., 2021). Finding the right balance between traditional methods and technological innovations can make Civil Technology teachers' work easy when preparing woodworking practical lessons that can accommodate all learners needs. Hence, in a classroom setting, teachers often encounter learners with varying levels of woodworking skills and experience. Thus, planning practical lessons that cater to beginners while also challenging more advanced learners can be a complex task. Moreover, woodworking teachers need to create lesson plans that are inclusive and allow all learners to learn and progress at their own pace (Oviawe & Omoh, 2021). In addressing these challenges, woodworking teachers can leverage their expertise, creativity, and instructional strategies to create engaging and enriching learning experiences for their learners.

TEACHING STRATEGIES IN WOODWORKING LESSONS

The German apprenticeship program for carpentry and woodworking is well-known across the globe because of its distinctive and all-encompassing approach to education (Young et al., 2019). Furthermore, the German model of dual studies vocational education and training (VET) is often described as a major contributor to the successes of the German Economy. Hence, in Germany, woodworking practical skills are often taught in schools as part of vocational education programs (Huang, 2021). These programs aim to provide students with hands-on experience and technical knowledge that can prepare them for careers in various trades. The strategies used in teaching woodworking practical skills in Germany schools typically involve a combination of theoretical instruction and practical training (BALA, 2021). In the first year, students attend vocational school full-time to learn the fundamentals of woodworking, including theory and practical skills. Furthermore, students begin by hands-on training and graphics as means of communication which include drawing of plans for their simulations. However, one of the key strategies used in teaching woodworking practical skills is hands-on training (Igaru, 2023). Students have the opportunity to work with different tools and materials under the guidance of experienced teachers. This hands-on approach allows students to develop their skills through practice and experimentation (Liu & Fang, 2023). In the first year, safety is a top priority in woodworking classes, and students are taught proper safety protocols from the beginning (Chatigny, 2022). This includes instruction on how to use tools safely, how to handle materials correctly, and how to maintain a clean and organized workspace to prevent accidents (Msimango & Mtshali, 2024). In the second and third years, students complete their apprenticeship in the dual system, spending four days a week in a training company and one day in vocational school.

Here, the students acquire woodworking practical skills under the guidance of their teacher while continuing to develop their theoretical knowledge. Teachers in Germany schools often provide individualized instruction to students based on their skill level and learning pace (Tetzlaff et al., 2021). Also, Maghsudi et al. (2021) emphasize that personalized approach allows students to progress at their own speed and receive the support they need to succeed. The German education system that focuses on woodworking and carpentry is unique in that it strikes the ideal mix between theory and practice (Hordern, 2021). Throughout the course woodworking classes often incorporate Project-Based Learning (PBL), where students are tasked with completing specific projects that require them to apply their skills and knowledge. This hands-on approach helps students see the practical applications of what they are learning. In addition to classroom instruction, many vocational education programs that offer apprenticeship opportunities where students can gain real-world experience working alongside skilled professionals in woodworking shops or construction sites. According to Arthur-Mensah (2015) the strategies used in teaching woodworking practical skills in schools focus on providing students with a well-rounded education that combines theoretical knowledge with practical experience, ensuring they are well-prepared for careers in the woodworking industry.

In Zimbabwe, teaching strategies in woodworking lessons play a crucial role in imparting knowledge and skills to students effectively (Katsande, 2023). Hence the Wood Technology and Design curriculum emphasizes the development of hands-on skills, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking among learners. However, to achieve these educational objectives, woodworking teachers can employ various teaching strategies tailored to the subject matter and the needs of the learners. According to Okillan Asianut (2021), the most effective teaching strategies in

woodworking lessons is hands-on practical activities. Therefore, learners learn best by doing, so providing them with opportunities to work with wood, tools, and equipment helps reinforce theoretical concepts and enhances their understanding of woodworking techniques. Furthermore, the effective teaching strategy of practical lessons in woodworking is through practical demonstrations where teachers showcase woodworking techniques, tool handling, and safety practices (Hayner, 2022). This hands-on approach allows learners to observe and learn by doing, enhancing their understanding of the subject. Thus, implementing project-based learning activities in woodworking classes can engage learners actively (Karan & Brown, 2022). By assigning projects that require planning, designing, and constructing woodwork pieces, learners can apply theoretical knowledge into practical skills.

Woodworking lessons in South Africa often require effective teaching strategies to engage learners and impart hands-on practical skills. Therefore, teachers utilize various methods to ensure that learners grasp the concepts and techniques involved in woodworking (Lee, 2023). Yet Li et al. (2018) mentioned that the most effective teaching strategies in woodworking lessons is hands-on learning. As, learners benefit greatly from actively engaging with tools, materials, and projects. This approach allows them to develop practical skills through direct experience, leading to better retention and understanding of woodworking concepts (Wagner et al., 2021). Yet, teachers often use demonstrations and visual aids such as diagrams, videos, and slideshows to explain woodworking techniques and processes. However, visual representations help learners visualize complex procedures and understand the steps involved in completing a project (Nkosi & Mtshali, 2024). Moreover, visual representations can be of great influence to effective teaching in schools around uMgungundlovu, KwaZulu Natal of South Africa because it may assist teachers to conduct woodworking practical lessons effectively against the limited time from the schools' academic time-tables. Also, the Project-based learning (PBL) is a popular teaching strategy in woodworking lessons where learners work on real-life projects from start to finish. In uMgungundlovu District teachers promote PBL through Civil Technology Practical Assessment Task (PAT) to ensure learners master the woodworking craftsmanship (Msimango, 2024). This hands-on approach not only enhances technical skills but also fosters creativity, problem-solving abilities, and teamwork among students. However, a lot of challenges emerge that hinder all these effective strategies to take place. It is unfortunate that a number of studies have been conducted to support the existence of these challenges in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal of South Africa but the KwaZulu Natal Department of Education (KZNDOE) has overlooked such concerns hence they still exist even to date. However, by incorporating these teaching strategies into woodworking lessons in South Africa, teachers can create engaging learning environments that empower learners to develop both technical skills and creativity in the field of woodworking.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

PEDAGOGICAL DESIGN CAPACITY

Pedagogical design capacity (PDC) is the teacher's ability and competence to perceive and use both personal teacher resources (i.e. knowledge, beliefs, identity, and orientations) and external curriculum resources to craft a learning environment in the context of instructional goals or objectives (Brown, 2002, 2008). Furthermore, Brown (2011), summarise DPC as a framework that explains "a teacher's capacity to perceive and mobilize existing resources in order to craft instructional episodes". In Technology-related subjects, like as Civil Technology it looks at teaching as a design activity and considers how teachers use resources to develop hands-on skills lessons that support effective teaching and learning in the woodworking workshop. Thus, in Brown's (2009) original conception, PDC includes both curriculum resources (physical objects, domain representations, and procedures) and teacher resources (subject matter knowledge, beliefs, and PCK). Furthermore, our understanding of the patterns in the lesson plans prepared by Civil Technology teachers emerges from the pedagogical design capabilities.

However, Civil Technology teachers' enactments of curriculum are influenced by both Curriculum Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) and teacher resources and can include offloading, adapting, or improvising of the curriculum resources. Brown (2009) argues that sometimes teachers improvise and design their own instructional episodes relying to a greater extent on their teaching resources, whereas other times teachers offload their agency and directly use curriculum. Still other times, teachers adapt curriculum to design instructional episodes that keep some components of the curriculum but also introduce new components influenced by their teacher resources (Brown, 2009). In this way, teachers use the Annual Teaching Plans (ATP)s and the CAPS document for instructional planning purposes can that is in line with the curriculum of South African schools (Ajani, 2021). Previous research using the PDC framework indicates that depending on their available resources and how those resources interact, teachers' instructional episode plans when enacting curriculum vary in terms of how productively they align with science education reform goals, such as argumentation (Davis et al., 2011; Remillard, 1999; Schwarz, 2009).

Since there aren't many technology education curricula that emphasize hands-on practice lessons for the woodworking subject in Civil Technology, this study employs a broader definition of PDC that encompasses all accessible instructional materials, not only curriculum. In particular, this study makes the case that teachers of Civil Technology can use instructional planning workshops, the CAPS document, and other tools and equipment to create lesson plans for practical woodworking lessons in that teachers are expected to improvise, adapt, or offload. The study we employ DPC construct that explains teachers' curricular decisions with three patterns of curriculum use—offloading, adapting, and improvising. However, this study will adopt all the three above-mentioned patterns of this theory. Where, offloading refers to high adherence to the curriculum when curricular materials are used as is. Therefore, Civil Technology teachers will be using the CAPS document for curriculum needs guidance; also, the CAPS document help woodworking teachers to find a balance between theory and practical lessons as per curriculum describe all the Civil Technology's' subject specializations like woodworking (Msimango et al., 2024).

Yet, adapting refers to the practice of using original curriculum materials and modifying as necessary. In this case, the specific ATP for woodworking subject specialization is used for lesson planning where teachers' lesson plans must be coherent with the ATP to avoid any destructions that may emerge due inappropriate use of the ATP. Furthermore, for woodworking practical

lessons teachers also use the Practical Assessment Task (PAT) document as a tool to assist them when planning their practical lessons effectively. Lastly, improvising refers to the teacher practice of creating his or her own curriculum; as the finding from the previous studies revealed that Civil Technology teachers are faced by a number of challenges in their workplaces and where they have to improvise. After all, these three patterns employed by this study also seek to promote the Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCD) because they assist teachers to reach their beliefs in the didactic situation. Though the framework of pedagogical design capacity clarifies distinct stages of curriculum use, the patterns are not necessarily developmental, pertaining to practicing teachers only.

Figure 1. Browns' (2009) framework for DPC

Figure 1, which presents our adaptation of Brown's (2009) framework for PDC. The right side of Figure 1, the teacher resources, aligns with Brown's original conception (2009) and includes their subject matter knowledge, PCK, and beliefs (Brown, 2009). Whereas subject matter knowledge pertains to what Civil Technology content the teacher knows (the what), PCK is concerned with how to best teach woodworking practical lessons (the how). Beliefs, in comparison, attend to the motivation behind instructional choices (the why). A number of studies were conducted in relation to teaching of practical lessons for technical subjects like Civil Technology but worrisome findings emerged as the range of teachers were observed failing to adapt curricular. First, Mtshali and Msimango (2023) results suggested that some Civil Technology teachers' misunderstood demonstration as means of teaching strategy for practical lessons, which also influence how they enacted the curriculum materials. Similarly, in a study conducted by Davis' and her colleagues (2011) made changes to the reform-oriented curriculum based on her learning goals, and the goals did not match that of the curriculum. Specifically, the teacher did not recognize the importance of scientific explanation, and dismissed the curricular resources that supported this goal. The results to both studies suggest that we need to better understand how teachers draw upon their instructional and personal resources to design instruction. In this study, the researcher did explore Civil Technology teachers' PDC by examining how teachers' PCK and beliefs impact their design and implementation of argumentation within their instruction.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH APPROACH

In this study, a qualitative methodology was used. In qualitative research, ideas, opinions, or experiences are investigated through the collection and analysis of non-numerical data (Chai et al., 2021). It is used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research. Furthermore, this research method was adopted in this study primarily because of its capacity to obtain comprehensive insights into an issue. Creswell (2017), support that qualitative research is concerned with understanding participants' views, experiences, beliefs, ideals, thoughts, and actions regarding social or human problems. Thus, the qualitative approach was deemed relevant because the researcher had to understand how Civil Technology's woodwork teachers prepare for their practical lessons and the teachers' responses were acquired using document analysis and semi-structured interviews as data collection tools which assisted the study in ascertaining this.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A case study research design was employed in this study. A case study research design is a methodological approach used in various fields such as academic field of research to conduct an in-depth investigation of a specific subject (Priya, 2021). This design involves studying a particular case, which could be an individual, group, organization, event, or phenomenon, to gain detailed insights and understanding. According to Paparini et al. (2020), case study research method provides a rich context, making it possible to explore variables in real-life settings that might be difficult to examine through other research method. This study, however, focused on technical and secondary schools that provide woodworking as a Civil Technology subject specialization to learners in grades ten (10) through twelve (12). Moreover, the researcher decided to holistically embed the cases of this study to examine the problem since a similar study in the Technology and Vocational Education (TVE) sector are not yet done. Therefore, this design was best suited for this study because it sought an in-depth perception of the effectiveness of the use of lesson plans for effective teaching of woodworking practical lessons in uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal of South Africa.

POPULATION

This study purposively sampled five (5) schools from uMgungundlovu District, KwaZulu Natal of South Africa. Purposive sampling is a technique used in qualitative research to select a specific group of individuals or units for analysis (Campbell et al., 2020). However, the purpose or objective the researcher employed purposive sampling was because of the experience and qualifications the participants have for teaching of woodworking which will provide the assurance of the findings from this study. Therefore, each of the eight (8) participants in the study was a teacher, meaning that there was more than one teacher per school in certain cases due to the school having more than one (1) teacher per school for the Civil Technology specialization in woodworking. Pseudonym names were used to identify the participants.

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

This study used two methods in the collection of data; namely document analysis and semi-structured interviews as data collection tools. However, In qualitative research, data collecting is the act of obtaining non-numerical information through interviews, pictures, and observations in order to comprehend people's attitudes, behaviors, beliefs, and motives within a particular setting (Williams & Cutler, 2020). Also, Creswell (2013) alluded that the instruments to be used must enable participants to express their views. In this case, participants were allowed or given the leverage to express their views freely without being restricted which led to greater data validity. Any research design's fundamental component is thought to be data collection. The two and three research questions were the focus of the semi-structured interviews (3). According to Croucher and Cronn-Mills (2021), semi-structured interview questions are a blend of predetermined and open-ended questions designed to facilitate a flexible yet focused conversation between the interviewer and the participant. In this study, the researchers employed this type of data collection tool because allows the interviewer to explore specific topics while also providing room for spontaneous follow-up questions based on the participant's responses. In addition, semi-structured interview questions serve as a vital tool in this study (qualitative research) by balancing structure with flexibility, enabling researchers to obtain comprehensive insights into participants' perspectives. While document analysis sought to understand how woodworking teachers plan their woodworking practical lessons in order to facilitate effective teaching and learning. Morgan (2022), define document analysis as a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating documents, both printed and electronic, to extract meaningful information and insights. This qualitative research method involves examining and interpreting data from lesson plan documents to gain understanding, uncover teaching methods, and develop empirical knowledge about effective teaching of woodworking practical lessons in the workshop.

DATA ANALYSIS

To enable the researcher to draw conclusions and summarize findings, data analysis is the act of methodically going through and organizing transcripts, field notes, interviews, and other materials that have been gathered (Leedy & Ormrod, 1980). This study adapted a thematic data analysis method. According to Terry and Hayfield (2020) thematic analysis is a qualitative method that involves reading through a data set, such as transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups, and identifying patterns in meaning across the data to derive themes. Furthermore, Terry and Hayfield (2020) emphasize that this method requires an active process of reflexivity, where the researcher's subjective experience plays a central role in deriving meaning from the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before reporting on the findings, it is important to display the biographical data of the cohort that participated in this study. Thus, the biographical data for the participants is attached below in figure 1.

Name(s)	Gender	Age-range	Number of years teaching woodworking?	Qualification(s)	Attended CAPS Skills-Training for woodworking?
Teacher A	Male	30-35	5	B. Ed: (Hons)	Yes
Teacher B	Male	30-35	6	B. Ed	Yes
Teacher C	Female	20-25	3	B. Ed	Yes
Teacher D	Male	30-35	1	B. Ed:	No
Teacher E	Male	45-50	21	N. Dip: Civil Engineering ACE: Technology Education	Yes
Teacher F	Female	30-35	6	B. Ed: (Hons)	Yes
Teacher G	Male	30-35	4	B. Ed: (Hons)	Yes
Teacher H	Male	30-35	5	B. Ed	Yes

Figure 1. Summary of participants' biographical data

The section that follows provides an overview of the participants who took part in the study and gives the findings based on the research questions. Thus, document analysis was used to arrive at the findings for Research Question One (RQ1). Then, semi-structured interview questions pertinent to the lesson planning and teaching environment of Civil Technology's woodworking subject specialization were used to gather data for Research Questions Two (RQ2) and Three (RQ3).

RESEARCH QUESTION ONE (RQ1) FINDINGS

Research question one (How do woodworking teachers plan their practical lessons?). This research question was primarily answered using data from document analysis where lesson plans for woodworking practical lesson plans were prepared by the participants were scrutinized. As per Browns' (2009) framework for DPC, was the tenet applicable to this research question. Since Browns' (2009) framework for DPC proposed three patterns for effective lesson planning for this theory. Therefore, this research question was conducted in guidance by one of those patterns called offloading. So, this study discovered the following themes to be used by Civil Technology's woodworking teachers when preparing their practical lessons. Namely:

- Indicating the lesson topic of the practical task.
- Creating lesson objectives to carry out the practical lesson,
- Preparing a cutting list,
- Attaching the activity and marking rubric

Indeed, Milkova (2012) maintain that instructional planning should contain the components outlined above, thus this study believed that those were key components to address how woodworking specialisation teachers planned practical lessons for effective teaching. Nevertheless, each of the aforementioned emergent components were elaborated upon below as themes that may promote effective teaching of woodworking practical lessons:

Table 1. Theme 1

THEME 1: Indicating A Topic of The Practical Task	
Lesson plan documents were collected from the Civil Technology woodworking subject teachers and then thoroughly analyzed. Below are the findings from teachers' lesson plan documents that were analyzed by the researcher(s)	
Teacher(s)	Findings
Teacher A	Clearly indicated
Teacher H	Clearly indicated
Teacher E	Clearly indicated

Table 2. Theme 2

THEME 2: Creating Lesson Objectives to Carry Out the Practical Lesson	
Lesson plan documents were collected from the Civil Technology woodworking subject teachers in order to know and understand the lesson objectives. Below are the findings from teachers' lesson plan documents that were analyzed by the researcher(s)	
Teacher(s)	Findings
Teacher A	Clearly indicated
Teacher H	Clearly indicated
Teacher E	Clearly indicated

Table 3. Theme 3

THEME 3: Preparing A Cutting List	
Lesson plan documents were collected from the Civil Technology woodworking subject teachers to find out if the teacher did prepare and attach the cutting list. Below are the findings from teachers' lesson plan documents that were analyzed by the researcher(s)	
Teacher(s)	Findings
Teacher A	The cutting list was prepared and attached behind the lesson plan
Teacher B	The teacher used the cutting list from the PAT document, no lesson plan was prepared
Teacher C	Although there was no lesson plan prepared but the teacher had the cutting list from the PAT document
Teacher D	The teacher had a cutting list at hand
Teacher E	The cutting list was prepared and attached behind the lesson plan
Teacher F	The teacher used the cutting list from the PAT document, no lesson plan was prepared
Teacher G	The teacher used the cutting list from the PAT document, no lesson plan was prepared
Teacher H	Although the cutting list was attached to the lesson plan but it was not self-prepared by the teacher

Table 4. Theme 4

THEME 4: Attaching The Activity and Marking Rubric	
Using both teachers' PAT management plan and the lesson plan documents; these documents were thoroughly analyzed to check if the class activity and the marking rubric were attached. Below are the findings from teachers' lesson plan documents that were analyzed by the researcher(s)	
Teacher(s)	Findings
Teacher A	Both the detailed activity and the marking rubric was attached together with the lesson plan
Teacher B	The teacher used the PAT document for marking the simulations
Teacher C	The teacher used the PAT document for marking the practical activity
Teacher D	The teacher used the PAT document for marking purposes, hence the document has the marking guidelines/rubric
Teacher E	activity and the marking rubric were attached together with the lesson plan and the PAT document
Teacher F	The teacher used the PAT document for marking purposes, hence the document has the marking guidelines/rubric
Teacher G	The teacher used the PAT document for marking purposes, hence the document has the marking guidelines/rubric
Teacher H	activity and the marking rubric were attached together with the lesson plan

Although Milkova (2012) state that it is obligatory that a topic for the specific lesson be indicated on the planning document (lesson plan). Thus, the participants were expected to submit a well-prepared lesson plan to the researcher prior their woodworking practical lessons. However, from the on-set, only three (3) participants presented the documented plans for their practical lessons. Hence, the above-displayed table(s) show only three (3) teachers' lesson plans (Teacher A, H and Teacher E) who submitted the lesson plans while the remaining five (5) participants (Teacher B, C,

G, F and D) had not prepared and presented a documented lesson plan for their practical lessons. This made it difficult for the researchers to find the objectives of the lesson since they were not written anywhere because of instructional planning. Yet, Lesson objectives help create an effective lesson that results in the desired learning outcome, claim (Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019). Any lesson plan must include objectives that outline the goals you, as the teacher, hope to accomplish by the end of the class. Furthermore, the majority of the participants never bother to prepare the cutting list and the activity with the marking rubric; instead, the teachers opted to use that marking rubrics from the Practical Assessment Task (PAT) document for marking purposes.

RESEARCH QUESTION TWO (RQ2) AND RESEARCH QUESTION THREE (RQ3) FINDINGS

Research question three (2) (What are the challenges faced by teachers in planning practical woodworking lessons?) Research question two (3) (What are the teaching strategies used by woodworking teachers in the uMgungundlovu District?) and were both responded to through semi-structured interviews. Given that the research question one explores woodworking teachers' strategies for teaching practical lessons in the workshop; and the research question two seeks to investigate the challenges faced by teachers in planning practical woodworking lessons. Thus, since Browns' (2009) framework for DPC proposed three patterns for effective lesson planning for this theory. Therefore, these research questions were conducted in guidance by two of those patterns namely adaptation and improvising. Thus, a competent teacher applies experiences and knowledge to provide hands-on guidance, establishes good relationship with the learners and also motivates them (Fjellström, 2014). Based on the findings of this study which developed two (2) themes that captures the strategies for teaching practical lessons for woodworking in the workshop, namely;

- Workshop readiness
- Demonstration

Therefore, the findings using the above-mentioned themes are elaborated upon below using a thematic map:

Figure 1. The findings for RQ2 and RQ3 (Source: Authors' own development)

Figure 1. above shows the findings acquired from research question two and research question three. Furthermore, the above model consists of five (5) challenges faced by teachers when planning for practical lessons which can be seen above in figure 1. constructed through workshop readiness theme. Also, figure 1. consist of four (4) strategies that may be used by Civil Technology teachers when conducting woodworking practical lessons; which were constructed through the demonstration theme.

This study presented findings based on the previously mentioned theoretical framework and that is Brown (2009) Pedagogical Design Capacity (PDC) which was used as guidance of this study. However, inquiry concerning Civil Technology' woodworking teachers' instructional planning for practical lessons was conducted through document analysis and semi-structured interviews. Therefore, for the research question one, this study was focusing on the lesson plan templates. Furthermore, the lesson plan documents were analysed thoroughly to check if the participants do have knowledge and skills of designing a lesson plan. Unfortunately, the majority of the participants did not prepare lesson plans and only these participants (Teacher A, H and Teacher E) who managed to prepare such document. Yet Farrell and Ashcraft (2024), does emphasize the significance of instructional planning for effective teaching and learning. However, the absence of a lesson plans from the majority of the participants proved that there is still a need for teachers to be taught about the significance of instructional planning. Submitting a lesson plan could have been an opportunity for Civil Technology's woodworking subject teachers to collaborate with the researcher and gain insights into their teaching practices. Jeong and So (2020), state not preparing the lesson play may not only affect teachers' effective teaching but it may develop learning difficulties for students. Therefore, it is important that teachers in uMgungundlovu District, in KwaZulu Natal, South Africa adapt into instructional planning. Also, for the research question one the document analysis was not only done for assessing if the teachers can adequately design a lesson plan. But this study used one of the three patterns called offloading in Brown (2009) Pedagogical Design Capacity (PDC) theoretical framework discussed above.

This pattern was basically focusing of how Civil Technology teachers adhere and comply with the curriculum delivery using the CAPS document as their guidance. Although the majority of the participants did not comply with the submission of their lesson plans; but this study confirm that Civil Technology's woodworking subject teachers does practice adequate curriculum delivery to the woodworking workshops and classroom at uMgungundlovu District of KwaZulu Natal in South Africa. That is confirmed because the Civil Technology Annual Teaching Plans (ATP) together with the Civil Technology PAT documents were always on hand when the teachers were conducting their woodworking practical lessons. The research question two, was also drilled using the last pattern from Brown (2009) theoretical framework which is improvising and the theme was workshop readiness hence this research question was about the teachers experience that take place in the workshop. The findings from this research question emerge that Civil Technology teachers does improvise due to a number a challenge that disturb lesson planning for woodworking practical lessons. The majority of the teachers mentioned that poor maintenance of the resources in their workshops, limited time for practical lessons and procurement processes in schools are the key effect that disturb them. However, due to the interest of the learners and curriculum delivery they end up taking the maintenance task to their hands hence the KZNDOE seem to oversight such concern. For the research question three, this study adopted demonstration as the theme and adaptation as the pattern from Brown (2009) PDC theoretical framework to make it easy for the researcher to conduct and analyze this research question accordingly. However, the findings showed that Civil Technology's woodworking subject teachers do adapt to any didactic situation to in order to ensure teaching is done effectively using any valuable teaching strategies for the best interest of the learners. Moreover, the findings show that most of the participants are opting for the hands-on demonstration of the woodworking craftsmanship in their schools. But some of the participants preferred using videos, images and textbooks as teaching strategy of woodworking practical lessons. These participants (Teachers B, C, and H) supported their use of videos for teaching practical woodworking skills, emphasizing time constraints and varying learner needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Previous studies have already been utilized to guarantee that pre-service teachers receive instructional planning training prior to their graduation. But it is unfortunate that once they start working, they tend to ignore the preparation of the lesson planning as a tool for successful lesson. Thus, this study will suggest that in addition to curriculum-based information and practical skills that teachers should be focused on, teacher trainings and workshops should also emphasize the development of effective teaching skills. Since effective lesson planning can also contribute to the Civil Technology teacher's own development of their woodworking hands-on skills; and that may assist them to champion learners' different needs in the classroom. Thus, effective lesson planning can contribute to job satisfaction when a lesson is successful or a learner does well on their woodworking practical assessments through PAT. Furthermore, this study emphasizes that having a skillfully-planned lesson can also make the act of teaching more pleasurable by increasing the teacher's confidence in themselves and letting them focus more on interaction with the learners than on what is supposed to happen next in their workshops. Importantly, good planning can save time by avoiding last-minute efforts to buy supplies or create materials needed for a day in the classroom (Prendergast & Lee, 2024). This means that Civil Technology's woodworking subject teachers can also be able to prepare for the practical lessons and keep

track on the resources from their workshops through their procurement records. Therefore, the ongoing instructional planning skills development programs must be arranged by the KZNDOE. Also, the KZNDOE must monitor teachers' subject files to promote and keep track of instructional planning processes in schools. In addition, schools revamp their procurement policies to support teachers and the subject needs, that can ensure there are not insufficient tools and equipment in the workshop. Lastly, this study recommends that technical subject teachers like Civil Technology must also be continuously trained for occupational health and safety in the workshop and their first-aid kits be maintained.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that factors like the poor maintenance of resources in schools and the time allocated to PAT for Civil Technology (woodworking) does impedes the effective instructional planning for practical lessons. Furthermore, this study conclude that video-assistance teaching is being practiced by teachers when teaching practical lessons in schools. This study investigated how woodworking teachers prepare their lesson plans for practical lessons. However, it was unfortunate that the results indicated that teachers do not practice lesson planning for the practical lessons. Instead, they use PAT management plan from the Civil Technology PAT document as the guidance of what needs to be done on that particular day scheduled for woodworking practical lessons. In the first research question, only three (3) teachers submitted the lesson plans, while the remaining five (5) opted for to not comply with the researcher's request. The responses from the research question one (1) left the researcher with the conclusion that the teachers do not practice lesson plan. The semi-interviews for research question two and three were discussed in this study revealed that Civil Technology teachers are fluent with their educational technologies and other relevant tool hence they can adapt and improvise when needed in order to ensure their teaching and learning is not disturbed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declare no conflict of interest.

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